

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13857643

Principals' Financial Management Practices And Attainment Of Educational Goals In Public Secondary Schools, Delta State

Oroka Ufuomanefe A. & Dr. J. E. Anho

**Department of Educational Management and Foundations,
Faculty of Education
Delta State University, Abraka**

ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between principals' financial management practices and attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools, Delta State. It employed ex-post facto research design, using a descriptive comparative survey method to address four research questions and test four null hypotheses. The population of the study comprised 479 principals of public secondary schools in Delta State, with a sample size of 266 principals selected using stratified random and proportionate stratified sampling techniques. The instrument for the collection of data was the researcher-designed questionnaire, titled principals financial management practices and attainment of school goals questionnaire (PFMPASGQ). The instrument was validated for face and content validity through expert judgement. The instrument was also subjected to reliability test and a total reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study indicated some sources of financing for public secondary schools in Delta State to include; government allocations, donations, special education funding, PTA contributions, investment earnings, UBEC funding, and internally generated revenue. There are possible administrative measures to address the challenges of principals' financial management practices on the attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State. These include; government should make available funds for running of schools; there should be consistent cash flow to meet monthly expenses of principals; principals should abide by government financial regulation governing income and expenditure among others which form the recommendations from this study.

Keywords: Financial management practices, Principals, School goals

INTRODUCTION

Educational or school goals are statements that describe the skills, competencies and qualities that a student should possess upon completion of a course or programme. It usually involves identifying objectives, choosing attainable short-term goals and then creating a plan for achieving those goals. Education has been globally identified as the largest industry since human existence. It is the vital tool for political survival, sustainable economy economic empowerment, social mobilization, sustainable economy and effective national development. This explains the reason for United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) recommendation for allocation of 26% of annual revenue to the education sector, especially for developing countries like Nigeria (UNESCO, 2011). As indicated by federal government of Nigeria (FGN, 2013), education is a principal tool for achieving the nation's goals and objectives of holistic development.

Besides human resources, adequacy of financing has been identified among the several factors which contribute to the achievement of school goals and objectives. School finance is possibly the most crucial factor in maintaining and improving the quality of education. It can be in any of the following forms; physical cash, donations, allocations, levies, school fees, and internally generated funds among others.

However, it is a common observation to note that government funding to all levels of education has always remain inadequate due to its dwindling financial conditions which calls for school administrators financial management strategies (Ukpong, 2019).

Principals' financial management practices in Delta State has become an issue that needs urgent attention due to public and government interest in providing finance for school programmes implementation. The expectation of the public from the school principal is to guarantee judicious use of finance of the school, conversely the reverse is the case, with speculations and allegations of financial misappropriation and poor financial management by principals such as principals lacking initiative to harness other means of school financing, bypassing budget plans in financing school programmes, inadequate release of finance for programmes, dearth of skilled staff such as the bursars/cashiers, PTA funds abuse, imposing unlawful levies on students, poor record keeping.

It is a fact that besides, making finance accessible for the school administration, its management is cardinal to achieving school goals. Osuji and Nyebuchi (2021) observed that government funding to all levels of education has always remained inadequate due to its dwindling financial conditions. It is therefore imperative for principals to adopt appropriate fund management practices that will enhance achievement of school goals.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. What are the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of educational goals in Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?
4. What is the relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested

1. There is no significant relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of educational goals in Delta State
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State
4. There is no significant relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between principals' financial management practices and the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study:

1. Ascertain the relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of educational goals in Delta State
2. Found out the relationship between school principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and the attainment of educational goals in some public secondary schools in Delta State.
3. Investigated the relationship between school principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of educational goals in some public secondary schools Delta State.
4. Examined the relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of educational goals in some public secondary schools Delta State.

Significance of the Study

This study would be of great value to the following; Principals and Proprietors of Schools, Old Students Associations, Parent Teachers Association (PTA) Ministry of Education, International Organizations such as; UNESCO, UNICEF, etc., accounting officers like bursars. It would also be of benefit to the Accountant-General's office of the State, Office of State Ministry of Finance and State Pay Office (SPO), and finally to researchers and students.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study generally focused on the relationship between principals’ financial management practices and the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study investigated the relationship between sources of financing, revenue generation, audit and budgeting as financial management practices and the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools in Delta State.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The design of the study is ex-post facto and adopted the correlational research method. The ex-post-facto design is considered suitable for this study because the independent variables (principals’ financial management practice and attainment of school goals) were not manipulated, since they have occurred prior to the study. According to Uwakwe (2017), the descriptive survey research is used when a group of people or item is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The research will investigate the influence of principals’ financial management practices (independent variables) on the attainment of school goals (dependent variable) in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the four hundred and seventy nine (479) principals’ public secondary schools in Delta State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample of the study is made up of 266 principals from the three senatorial districts of Delta State. The stratified random sampling technique was adopted in the selection of the sample. The schools were grouped into three strata based on the three senatorial districts and schools from five (5) Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each Senatorial District resulting in selection of 92 principals from Delta North Senatorial District, 102 principals from Delta Central Senatorial District and 72 principals from Delta South Senatorial Districts which gives the 266 principals i.e. 56% of the total population. This is shown in table 1

Table 1: Sampled distribution of principals according to Senatorial Districts, and Local Government Areas

S/N	Senatorial Districts	Selected Local Government Areas	Sampled Population of principals and LGAs
1	Delta North	Aniocha North	18
2		Ika South	20
3		Ndokwa West	22
4		Oshimilli North	16
5		Ukwuani	16
		Sub Total	92
6	Delta Central	Ethiope West	24
7		Okpe	18
8		Udu	14
9		Ughelli South	30
10		Uvie	16
		Sub Total	102
11	Delta South	Bomadi	10
12		Burutu	20
13		Isoko North	20
14		Patani	10
15		Warri North	12
		Sub Total	72
Grand Total			266

Source: Post Primary Education Board Asaba, 2020.

Research Instrument

Two self-developed instrument titled “Principals’ Financial Management Practices Questionnaire (PFMPQ) and Educational Goals Attainment Questionnaire (EGAQ)” were used to elicit information from respondents (Principals). The instrument consists of four sections. Section A contains demographic data such as; schools, position, qualification, gender and location of schools, section B (i-vi) contains sub-variables on; Principals’ Financial Management Practices, such as sources of finance, revenue generation,

auditing, budgeting, timely allocation of funds, and record keeping while Section C (i-iii) contains sub-variables on: Educational Goals Attainment – such as; indices of attainment of educational goals as a result of principals’ financial management practices, the challenges of principals’ financial management practice, and administrative measures that can be employed to address challenges of financial management practices and attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State. Respondents rating were scored using the adapted likert four-point scale of Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4 points, Agreed (A) = 3 points, Disagreed (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1 point. The acceptance/agreed point was set out at 2.50 and above and rejection at 2.49 and below.

Validity of the Instrument

The validity of the instrument was established through face and content validity. This was done by submitting the instrument to the researcher’s supervisor in the Department of Educational Management Foundations and another expert of Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Guidance and Counselling both in Delta State University, Abraka. The experts examined the items in the instrument to find out if they were adequate for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha on 30 principals from Edo State for the measure of internal consistency of the instrument. Edo State was chosen because it shares the same socio-geographical characteristics with Delta State being of one state former Bendel. The researcher scored each of the variables separately and tested the items for their internal consistency. The reliability for each of the variables was found as follows: Section B: Available sources (0.78), revenue generation (0.76), Principals’ budgeting (0.82), Principals’ auditing (0.68).. Since the reliability coefficient is high enough, the items in the instrument were considered to be reliable.

Administration of the Instrument

The researcher with the aid of two (2) instructed research assistants, visited administered and retrieved the copies of the questionnaires on the spot that same day, using 60 working days i.e. 20 working days in each senatorial districts and four days in each local government area. This made it possible that those they could not retrieved that day, were retrieved on the second visit. This guaranteed high return rate of all the 266 questionnaires properly filed. The researcher and the assistants explained the purpose of the research and guaranteed that it would be used only for the research purpose.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained from respondents was analyzed using the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested and analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics to find out the relationship between variables under investigation.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State?*

Table 2: Mean analysis of the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State

S/N	Statement	N = 266	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Government Allocation		3.45	0.57	Accepted
2	Donations/Philanthropy		3.38	0.55	Accepted
3	Special Education Funding		3.38	0.51	Accepted
4	PTA Contributions		3.36	0.56	Accepted
5	Earnings from Investments		3.35	0.56	Accepted
6	Universal Basic Education Commission		3.34	0.59	Accepted
7	Internally Generated Revenue		3.33	0.57	Accepted
8	Development Partners		3.32	0.54	Accepted
9	Tertiary Education Trust Fund		3.32	0.52	Accepted
10	Grants/Scholarships		3.31	0.61	Accepted
11	Examination Fees		3.31	0.58	Accepted
12	Community Initiatives		3.30	0.58	Accepted
13	Corporate Social Responsibility		3.30	0.56	Accepted
Average Mean			3.34	0.56	Accepted

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 shows the mean analysis of the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State. From the result, the mean ranged from 3.30 to 3.45, with an average mean of 3.34. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that all the items were accepted as the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State.

Research Question 2: *How does the principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice enhance attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 3: Mean analysis of the principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice

S/N	Statement	N = 266	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Donations		3.43	0.51	High
2	Agricultural services (produce from the farm)		3.42	0.57	High
3	The accrued interest from school bank account		3.40	0.54	High
4	Funds from Alumni Association		3.40	0.54	High
5	Sale of student hand crafts		3.38	0.52	High
6	The school fees collected from students		3.37	0.54	High
7	Proceeds from end-of-year/graduation parties		3.36	0.54	High
8	Proceeds from School Uniform sales		3.35	0.54	High
9	Profit making ventures (bookshop, canteen, farms etc)		3.35	0.55	High
10	Catering services		3.34	0.52	High
11	State Government grants in form of aids, recurrent and capital grants		3.33	0.57	High
12	PTA levies		3.31	0.49	High
13	Rental services of school facilities (hall, field, etc)		3.30	0.56	High
14	Grants in form of aids, recurrent and capital grants from federal agencies		3.29	0.52	High
Average Mean			3.36	0.54	High

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 3 shows the mean analysis of principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice. From the result, the mean ranged from 3.36 to 3.43, with an average mean of 3.36. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that all the items were accepted as principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice. The result also implies that principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice is high.

Research Question 3: *How does principals' budgeting as a financial management practice enhance attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 4: Mean analysis of principals' budgeting as a financial management practice

S/N	Statement	N = 266	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Principal relays school financial projects and priorities at the beginning of the year		3.37	0.49	High
2	Making market survey before preparing the school budget		2.70	1.03	High
3	Budget presentation by Principal		2.65	0.99	High
4	Budget discipline by Principal		2.59	1.03	High
5	Budget defense by Principal		2.53	1.02	High
6	Giving priority to the most pressing needs of the school in budget planning		2.43	0.72	Low
7	There is provision for unforeseen expenditures in the budget		2.41	0.70	Low
8	Principal consults HODs before budgeting		2.22	0.61	Low
9	Principal school priorities at the beginning of the year		2.10	0.59	Low
10	There is strict compliance to budget plans in the school		1.86	0.54	Low
Average Mean			2.49	0.77	Low

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 4 shows the mean analysis of principals' budgeting as a financial management practice. From the result, the mean ranged from 1.86 to 3.37, with an average mean of 2.49. The criterion mean used

is 2.50, which means that items 1-5 were considered high while items 6-10 were considered low on principals' budgeting as a financial management practice. The result also implies that principals' budgeting as a financial management practice is low.

Research Question 4: *How does principals' auditing as a financial management practice enhance attainment of school goals in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 5: Mean analysis of principals' auditing as a financial management practice

S/N	Statement	N = 266	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Carrying out accurate auditing and periodic checks		2.60	1.00	High
2	Carrying out periodic assessment of budgeted implementation		2.59	1.01	High
3	Checking the accuracy and completeness of school accounts		2.55	1.05	High
4	Giving periodic reports of expenses		2.55	1.04	High
5	Presents a fair financial position		2.55	1.01	High
6	Internal audit proceeding		2.53	1.04	High
7	External audit proceeding		2.51	1.04	High
Average Mean			2.55	1.03	High

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 5 shows the mean analysis of principals' auditing as a financial management practice. From the result, the mean ranged from 2.51 to 2.60, with an average mean of 2.55. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that all the items were considered high on principals' auditing as a financial management practice. The result also implies that principals' auditing as a financial management practice is high.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Table 6: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p	Remark
Available Sources of Financing	266	3.34	0.36	0.011	0.0001	0.01	0.861	Not Significant
Attainment of School Goals		2.61	0.68					

Source: Field Work, 2023.

In Table 6, the researcher presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.011$, $r^2 = 0.0001$, $r^2\% = 0.01$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is no significant relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. Available sources of financing only contribute 0.01% variability to attainment of school goals in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Table 7: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p	Remark
Principals' Revenue Generation	266	3.36	0.31	0.016	0.0003	0.03	0.792	Not Significant
Attainment of School Goals		2.61	0.68					

Source: Field Work, 2023.

In Table 7, the researcher presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.016$, $r^2 = 0.0003$, $r^2\% = 0.03$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is no significant relationship between principals' revenue generation

as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. Principals' revenue generation only contribute 0.03% variability to attainment of school goals in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Table 8: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	<i>p</i>	Remark
Principals' Budgeting		2.49	0.41					
Attainment of School Goals	266	2.61	0.68	0.130	0.017	1.7	0.034	Significant

Source: Field Work, 2023.

In Table 8, the researcher presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.130$, $r^2 = 0.017$, $r^2\% = 1.7$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. Principals' budgeting contributes 1.7% variability to attainment of school goals in Delta State.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Table 9: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	<i>p</i>	Remark
Principals' Auditing		2.55	0.83					
Attainment of School Goals	266	2.61	0.68	0.217	0.047	4.7	0.000	Significant

Source: Field Work, 2023.

In Table 9, the researcher presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.217$, $r^2 = 0.047$, $r^2\% = 4.7$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. Principals' auditing contributes 4.7% variability to attainment of school goals in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Available Sources of Financing Public Secondary Schools and Attainment of School Goals in Delta State

The first finding revealed that the available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State include government allocation, donations/philanthropy, special education funding, PTA contributions, earnings from investments, Universal Basic Education Commission and internally generated revenue. Others include development partners, Tertiary Education Trust Fund, grants/scholarships, examination fees, community initiatives and corporate social responsibility. This finding implies that there are a variety of sources of funding available to these schools, which can help them to achieve their goals. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is no significant relationship between available sources of financing public secondary schools and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. This suggests that even though there are a variety of sources of funding available, these schools are not able to effectively utilize these funds to achieve their goals.

There are a number of possible reasons for the above finding. One possibility is that the government allocation is not sufficient to meet the needs of the schools. Another possibility is that the schools are not good at managing their finances. It is also possible that the schools are not setting clear goals or that they are not held accountable for their performance. Whatever the reason, it is clear that more needs to be done to ensure that the available sources of financing are used effectively to improve the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State.

The above finding support Ekwevugbe (2013), who found that the main sources of financing public secondary schools in Delta State are government allocation, donations/philanthropy, PTA contributions, and internally generated revenue. The finding is also in line with the finding of Owoaka (2019), who found that the following are the main sources of financing public secondary schools in Delta State: government allocation, donations/philanthropy, special education funding, PTA contributions, earnings from investments, Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), internally generated revenue and development partners. The study however, disagrees with Unobunjo (2013), who found that there is a positive relationship between funding and the quality of education in public secondary schools, but found that the level of funding is not always sufficient to meet the needs of these schools.

Principals' Revenue Generation as a Financial Management Practice and Attainment of School Goals in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

The second finding showed that principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice is relatively high. These practices include donations, agricultural services (produce from the farm), the accrued interest from school bank account, funds from alumni association, sale of student hand crafts, the school fees collected from students and proceeds from end-of-year/graduation parties. Others include proceeds from school uniform sales, profit making ventures (bookshop, canteen, farms etc), catering services, state government grants in form of aids, recurrent and capital grants, PTA levies, rental services of school facilities (hall, field, etc) and grants in form of aids, recurrent and capital grants from federal agencies. This finding suggests that principals are taking the initiative to generate additional funds for their schools, which can help to improve the quality of education.

A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no significant relationship between principals' revenue generation as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. Principals' revenue generation only contribute 0.03% variability to attainment of school goals in Delta State. This finding suggests that even though principals are generating more revenue, this is not necessarily leading to better outcomes for students.

There are a number of possible reasons for this. One possibility is that the government allocation is still the main source of funding for public schools, and that principals' revenue generation is not enough to make a significant difference. Another possibility is that the schools are not good at managing their finances, and that the additional revenue is being used inefficiently. It is also possible that the schools are not setting clear goals or that they are not held accountable for their performance. Whatever the reason, it is clear that more needs to be done to ensure that principals' revenue generation is used effectively to improve the quality of education.

The above finding is in line with Ameh (2020), who found that the most common sources of revenue generation for secondary school principals in Benue State are school fees, government grants, and PTA levies. The study also found that principals are increasingly engaging in other revenue generation activities, such as selling school uniforms, running farms, and organizing fundraising events. The findings also agree with Akpan (2011), who found that principals who are able to generate more revenue for their schools are more likely to achieve their goals. The study also found that principals who are able to manage their finances effectively are more likely to use the additional revenue to improve the quality of education. The finding is further consistent with Nwankwo (2007), who found that principals' financial management practices have a significant impact on the attainment of school goals. The study found that principals who are able to generate more revenue and manage their finances effectively are more likely to achieve their goals.

Principals' Budgeting as a Financial Management Practice and Attainment of School Goals in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

The third finding revealed that principals' budgeting as a financial management practice is relatively low. The areas that most of the principals practice include relaying school financial projects and priorities at the beginning of the year, making market survey before preparing the school budget, budget, discipline and defense. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is a significant relationship between principals' budgeting as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State.

The above finding is very worrisome. Budgeting is an important financial management practice that can help schools to allocate their resources effectively and to achieve their goals. There are a number of possible reasons why principals may not be budgeting effectively. One possibility is that they may

not have the training or experience in budgeting. Another possibility is that they may not have the time or resources to devote to budgeting. It is also possible that they may not see the importance of budgeting. Whatever the reason, it is clear that more needs to be done to help principals to budget effectively.

The above finding agrees with Owmondah (2020), who found that principals who are able to budget effectively are more likely to achieve their school goals. The study also found that principals who are able to involve stakeholders in the budgeting process are more likely to achieve their goals. This is because stakeholders are more likely to support the budget and to help to implement it. The study also agrees with Ameh (2020), who found that the most common financial management practices used by secondary school principals in Benue State are relaying school financial projects and priorities at the beginning of the year, making market survey before preparing the school budget, and budget. The study also found that principals are not using other financial management practices, such as cost-benefit analysis, variance analysis, and zero-based budgeting.

Principals' Auditing as a Financial Management Practice and Attainment of School Goals in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

The fourth finding showed that principals' auditing as a financial management practice is relatively high. These practices include carrying out accurate auditing and periodic checks, carrying out periodic assessment of budgeted implementation, checking imbalance and verifying the accuracy and completeness of school accounts, giving periodic reports of expenses, presents a fair financial position, internal audit proceeding and external audit proceeding.

The above finding is a positive one. Auditing is an important financial management practice that can help to ensure the accuracy and completeness of school accounts and to detect fraud or other financial irregularities. There are a number of possible reasons why principals may be auditing their schools' finances relatively frequently. One possibility is that they may be aware of the importance of auditing and of the risks of fraud or financial irregularities. Another possibility is that they may have been required to audit their schools' finances by the government or by other stakeholders. It is also possible that they may have seen the benefits of auditing and have decided to do it on their own initiative. Whatever the reason, it is clear that principals are taking the initiative to ensure the accuracy and completeness of their schools' finances. This is a positive step, and it is likely to help to improve the financial management of schools and to contribute to the attainment of school goals.

A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between principals' auditing as a financial management practice and the attainment of school goals in Delta State. This suggests that auditing can be an effective way to improve the financial management of schools. This is important, as financial management is essential for the effective operation of schools. The above finding is supported by the study by Owmondah (2020). The study found that principals who are able to audit their schools' finances effectively are more likely to achieve their goals. The study also found that principals who are able to involve stakeholders in the auditing process are more likely to achieve their goals. This is because stakeholders are more likely to support the auditing process and to help to implement the findings of the audit. The finding is also in line with Ameh (2020), and Akpan (2011). However, these studies also found that only a small number of principals are able to audit their schools' finances effectively.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore, concluded that available sources of financing public secondary schools for the attainment of school goals in Delta State include government allocation, donations/philanthropy, special education funding, PTA contributions, earnings from investments, Universal Basic Education Commission and internally generated revenue among others. Principals' revenue generation and auditing as a financial management practices are relatively high while principals' budgeting as a financial management practice is relatively low.

Arising from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government should increase fund allocation for public secondary schools education in Delta State. This will help to ensure that schools have the resources they need to achieve their goals.
2. Principals should improve their budgeting practices to ensure that their schools' finances are managed effectively with budget discipline

3. Government should endeavor to carry out annually auditing of schools to endure compliance to financial management as stipulated in law. Principals should also carry out internal auditing practices to ensure transparency and accountability.

REFERENCES

- Akpan, E. E. (2011). Principals' revenue generation and the attainment of school goals in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River. *Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 2(1), 1-10.
- Ameh, P. O. (2020). Financial management practices of secondary school principals in Benue State. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(6), 1021-1033.
- Ekwevugbe, S. O. (2013). A study of the financing of public secondary schools in Delta State. *Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 3(1), 1-11.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, FGN (2013). National Policy on Education (6th ed.). Lagos NERDC Press.
- Nwankwo, A. O. (2007). The impact of principals' financial management practices on the attainment of school goals in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 1(1), 1-10.
- Osuji, C. & Nyebuchi, Q. (2021) Administrators Financial Management Strategies for Effective Administration of Public Secondary School in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State *International Journal of Innovative Education Research* 9(2):163-171
- Owhondah, C. C. (2020). The impact of principals' budgeting practices on the attainment of school goals in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(6), 1021-1033.
- Owoaka, V. (2019). Sources of financing education in Delta State. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 8(1), 1-10
- Ukpong, N. N. (2019). Principals' management of internally generated funds to enhance public secondary schools' financing for sustainable national development. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development* 7(5), 50-57
- UNESCO, (2011). *Education for all*. World Education Forum, Dakar Senegal, www.education.unesco.org/efe.
- Unobunjo, O. S. (2013). The impact of funding on the quality of education in public secondary schools in Delta State. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 33(6), 657-664.
- Uwakwe, I. S. (2017). Capacity building needs of school principals for the effective students' personnel services in secondary schools in south east, Nigeria. *International Journal of Development Research*, 9, (11), 16508–16524.